

Assessment of Reproducibility in Nix

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Glossary

API	Application Programming Interface
build artifacts	Files produced by a build process, such as executable binaries
checksum	A cryptographic hash value computed on data to verify integrity
continuous integration	Automated software builds and tests often tied to version control
CPU	Central Processing Unit
downstream	The software using and depending on the current piece of software
hermetic build	A build process taking place in a isolated environment without the hosts machine environment having any effect ¹
hexadecimal	A number system with a base value of 16
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
I/O	Input and output
immutable	Read only, static value that cannot be changed after initialization
ISO	Optical disc Image; a container file format
Linux Filesystem Hierarchy Standard	A standard for file and directory placement under UNIX-like operating systems
PATH	A environmental variable telling the shell where to search for executable files
SSH	Secure Shell protocol for safe remote access

¹<https://bazel.build/basics/hermeticity>

stdout	The standard output stream attached to a process
supply chain	The components, libraries, tools, and processes used to develop, build, and publish a software artifact
upstream	The dependencies used in this software
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
vendoring	A technique to copy and commit the dependency directly into a project repository and circumvent the package manager ²
world readable	Every user on the system has reading permissions

²<https://docs.conan.io/2/devops/vendoring.html>

1 Introduction

Describing a build process like a function in mathematics seems logical. The same input i will produce an identical output o if the same build command f is used: $f(i) = o$. Unless specifically focused, this deterministic behaviour is often not enforced for software builds [8]. Everything after the source code, including the build artifacts, is hard to verify in those cases.

1.1 History

The article "Reflections on Trusting Trust" is a historical base exploring the software supply chain. Ken Thompson describes how one element of a software handling toolchain can be compromised. In his example, the C compiler injects possibly malicious code into the binary it is currently building. He modified the compiler to react if a specific pattern in the source code is recognized while building. Upon recognition, the compiler will inject his malicious sequence into the binary file. There are two patterns the modified compiler will recognize: (1) the login command of the Linux kernel and (2) the C compiler. Every user login will allow one additional known password. When recompiling the C compiler, the active malicious compiler will infect the newly created one. Even when updating the compiler version and rebuilding the kernel's login, the machine will stay compromised after building the non-malicious source code. Thompson's article describes not the possibility of an attack by modifying the source code of the target software but a "program-handling program". Besides compilers, this attack method can, for example, apply to assembler, loader or hardware microcode [46].

In December 2020, the SUNSPOT Malware brought attention to the topic of supply chains. The build process of a network performance monitoring tool is compromised by installing "SUNSPOT". This software waits until a specific Microsoft build process is active. It tampers with the input source code, modifying it before the compiler can read it. The malicious sequence SUNBURST is inserted in the source code, only to be removed once the compiling process stops reading it. The binary has been compromised without the version control system showing any changes. The software was distributed with a backdoor, which allowed the Malware author to access the client machines on which it was used. To stay hidden, SUNSPOT used several tactics to prevent itself from appearing in the build machines logs [11].

Another example is the liblzma library with CVE-2024-3094. The build process was modified instead of the source code itself. In the released tar archive, a `build-to-host.m4` file had been edited. Since no actual source code was modified, it could not be tracked back to it, but it had to be discovered by other means [35].

In 2013, "The Tor Project" implemented deterministic builds in fear of compromised builders [31]. The goal was for every individual to individually build and

possibly alert public builders in case differences were found. Later, the Debian project also started an effort to make builds reproducible. From this point on, the effort behind reproducible builds has kept growing.

1.2 Motivation

Particularly when looking at the history of compromised build processes, the option of not trusting a third-party builder looks inviting, especially for open-source projects with public repositories. If the build process is public and reproducible, anyone can report a faulty build that has been tampered with. This openness decreases the incentive for attacks against the build process and the developers, who are considered trusted by force. Reducing the possibility of attacks is a special concern if it aims for a target in sectors such as privacy, security, politics, journalism, or otherwise carries a high reward from the attacker's perspective.

Reproducible builds also require documentation about the specific software dependencies used to build and run the program. A fully documented environment can make introducing new contributors easier as they do not have to hunt for particular versions to install that might or might not work in combination. This is especially true if no documentation exists and the project is given to another developer. A simple list or script installing arbitrary dependency versions is not always future-proof because sometimes nothing prevents changes on the same version number.

1.3 Goal

This work centres on deterministic software builds that can be reproduced on a bit-by-bit basis. This work uses Nix as a build toolchain to test for non-determinism in software builds within a continuous integration pipeline environment. Nix already provides the ability to configure and reproduce hermetically isolated environments declaratively (see section 3.2.1). On the nixpkgs GitHub page³, numerous issues regarding reproducible builds have already been solved. It offers several tools and workarounds, even for simple problems regarding non-deterministic builds that might not be fixed upstream.

An automated evaluation regarding the reproducibility of single software build processes is explored, and an implementation of a CI pipeline tooling solution is made.

The advantages and disadvantages of implementing reproducible builds should be clear at the end of this work. It will also aim for the secondary target to bring more attention to those advantages. The following questions are the central points of this work:

³<https://github.com/NixOS/nixpkgs>

Question 1: How can the quantity of reproducible software builds in automated environments using Nix be determined or measured?

Question 2: How can the information gained from Q1 best be delivered to the developer in an attempt to make more software builds reproducible?

Question 3: Why can reproducible builds be relevant in a closed-source development environment for security-relevant applications?

1.4 Structure

This work will start with a literature review of reproducible builds (see section 2). Important core concepts about DevOps, reproducible builds, and Nix are explained in section 3. A short inspection of how the public nixpkgs repository handles non-reproducible packages is done in section 4. A practical approach is described in section 5, and testing results of it are discussed in section 6. A Summary in section 7 is followed by an outlook in section 8 to close this work.

2 Literature Review

Ken Thompson explores the question of whom to trust delivering non-malicious software binaries [46]. He is leading with the example of the C compiler and the UNIX login command. In his example, the initial compiler is part of a chicken-and-egg problem, and the machine's initial compiler binary is pulled from an external source. This binary is trusted and claims to be compiled from a specific source code. This claim, however, is not verifiable, and a decision is made to trust the binary supplier. The machine is compromised since the pulled compiler secretly contains malicious code to self-replicate into a new compiler version and modify the Linux kernel login. To get the last state of the machine that is not compromised, the OS would need to be reinstalled. This example shows that the blind trust put in a binary supplier can be a serious security risk.

With ever more present continuous software delivery efforts, the stability of that service depends heavily on correct machine configurations [26, 44]. Siebra et al. differentiate between software developers' focus on changes and operational teams' focus on stability and availability [43]. As a practical example, multiple solutions for infrastructure as code (see section 3.1.1) approaches are used to ensure a consistent and stable operation. The declarative approach to defining environments is comparable to using the Nix language. This effort for consistency is a recurring theme in the following sections.

Chris Lamb and Stefano Zacchiroli explore reproducible builds in the context of a software supply chain [25]. They introduce verification of build artifacts through cryptographic hashing. Reproducible builds enable this method of verifying artifacts. They explain the characteristics of deterministic and reproducible builds. They mention how reproducible builds are achieved and give examples of what might prevent them. They note that the verification to build reproducibly can have a high accuracy but is not guaranteed.

With the theoretical awareness of the advantages that reproducible builds can provide, Butler et al. use several interviews to inspect how common the actual awareness and implementation in business environments is [8]. They found that the authors and interviewees had mixed knowledge about reproducible builds. The areas they found reproducible builds valuable are Open Source Software and complex yet safety-critical systems. Reasons for adoption focus on the ability to verify binaries in forensic use cases and provide a personal feeling of safety. In another case, reproducible builds were categorized as not having enough tangible impact and thus are unnecessary. No universal opinion on the topic was found.

As a consequence of the Solarwinds attack mentioned in section 1.1, Fourné et al. interviewed 24 participants from the Reproducible-Builds.org project [16]. They differentiate between reproducible and repeatable builds, with the latter not producing bit-by-bit identical artifacts. They found that the interest in reproducible builds was

primarily intrinsic and originating from the developers. The most significant issues preventing wider adoption they found are communication and willingness of upstream Developers, compiler-introduced non-determinism, embedded cryptographic signatures or hardware, and finally, a high understanding of the reproducible builds project, which might not be as attractive to work on as other topics.

In 2006, Eelco Dolstra released his thesis about a purely functional software deployment model called Nix [13]. He explores reoccurring problems with traditional deployment strategies and proposes a solution developed into the Nix build system since then. Most notable are some core concepts used in Nix that take memory management from programming to apply them at the file system level. Nix includes a dedicated language, a static software component deployment description format, and a software component store. These concepts and components are explained in section 3.3.

Nix claims to provide reproducibility of built environments. Malka et al. empirically evaluate if space and time reproducibility of build environments can be achieved using Nix [29]. They tried to rebuild software versions from around 2018, six years later. They could rebuild 99,94% of those 7 010 516 packages. Their findings reinforce the decision to use Nix as a build tool to define reproducible build environments to test for reproducible software builds.

Schwaighofer et al. propose metadata additions to the Nix build system [42]. They would provide additional provenance data for a built package. It would specify where a package is built and where each used dependency has been built. If a binary cache provides a package obtained from another binary cache, it would be available information. The metadata would also include a content hash, mapping the input hash to a content hash. The content hash addition targets cloud-based build systems to enable a safer distributed ecosystem of multiple independent builders and caches. Currently, a whole cache is trusted and not on a per-package basis. There is presently no verifiable information about the origin of those provided packages. It is merely trusted that the cache safely obtained the package. It shows the current situation where the trusting trust problem applies without an ability to verify non-reproducible builds [46]. The proposed changes to add provenance data to build results enable two possible ways to trust that the package content is correct:

1. Trusted Origin System: The specified builder is declared as a trusted source. The trusting trust problem still applies, but more transparency about the build server is provided.
2. Reproducible builds: Multiple independent caches build a package and provide an identical content hash. The package content is verified to be a result of an uncompromised build.

3 Theoretical Background

This chapter will focus on design principles regarding automation, building source code, and the Nix build system.

3.1 Developer Operations

Developer Operations (DevOps) describes practices that bridge the gap between the developer’s goal of change and the operator’s goal of stability.

3.1.1 Infrastructure as Code

“Infrastructure as Code” is a principle of DevOps. Source code, in and of itself, does not make the usable software. Another component is the environment on a machine for the software to (1) be built and (2) be executed. A conservative setup done manually is more prone to errors than an automated setup written in some variation of code [43].

The environment setup should generally be documented in code due to benefits like sharing, version control, and testing [43]. There are plenty of solutions that are either imperative or declarative. Regardless, they all aim to automate the setup of the environment.

The imperative approach reads like a set of instructions. They are executed after each other. This approach demonstrates the way from the machine’s default state to the targeted state. The initial machine state is most likely a “clean” state, which is present after a fresh operating system installation.

The declarative approach is structured like a configuration file. It is a description of the machine in its target state. There are no sequential instructions on how this targeted state is achieved. It is a separate job of the tooling to transition between the machine’s states.

Automation eliminates some errors that will otherwise appear sooner or later when every machine is manually configured. Automation also simplifies the setup of development environments to compile and test on multiple machines. This applies to new machines and new contributors who are not yet familiar with the project’s specific components [43].

3.1.2 Continuous Integration

One of those principles is practicing continuous integration, a regular and fine-grained fusion of new features into the master source code. This opportunity is used for several automated tests. CI is best done with an automated pipeline for building and testing changes made to the source code. This results in smaller merge requests on tagged branches.

This tactic provides a faster feedback loop for developers and their source code changes. In the case of issues, a required rollback can be smaller. Because of the defined tests, the relationship between deployment and development is more transparent for everyone involved.

3.1.3 DevSecOps

DevSecOps is a sub-field of DevOps, that includes security as a significant objective. Security-relevant checks extend the usual automated tests.

The information provided by automated tests is especially relevant in this work. The Method to find non-determinism or a non-reproducible build is done in the testing stage. Since a software build can require many computing resources, the build should not be a local task on the developer’s machine. A dedicated continuous integration runner can build and report findings asynchronously. In the case of a second build, a dedicated build server could be used not to disturb the run-time of the first software build and tests [33, 41].

3.2 Reproducible builds

A reproducible build is defined by producing a bit-by-bit identical output when executing with identical input [36]. A deterministic build is also described as a build that produces a bit-by-bit identical artifact, but it is explicitly assumed that the built environment does not change [10]. The term “reproducible build” will be handled as a synonym for “deterministic build” in the following chapters because the Nix build system will handle the built environment. Some exceptions like hardware-bound microcode apply.

First, clarifying what constitutes input when creating source code is essential. The source code itself is only one of the inputs. A software build process uses (1) source code with (2) build dependencies and the environment to output a result in the form of (3) build artifacts (see Figure 1). In traditional open source, everyone can look at the source code used to produce the built artifacts. If multiple people build the same source code multiple times in the same environment, it might be possible to create different build artifacts.

In many cases, software builds are not reproducible for historical reasons. In most cases, the build process will include a timestamp as metadata. This does not include the filesystem timestamp metadata because it can be easily manipulated at some later point in time. The timestamp could, for example, be in a header section of a binary build artifact. With timestamps included inside the build artifacts, even if the same source code has been used, the build artifacts are different every time. A typical example is the `__DATE__` macro available in C. Besides timestamps, other

Figure 1: Software build process: (1) raw source code; (2) environment to build artifacts; (3) build results

sources for non-determinism can be random number generators or single-use keys to sign the build artifacts [25].

More widely known but insufficient for reproducible builds is the “Software Bill of Materials” (SBOM). It is a documentation of every third-party component version that is used. Because an SBOM only documents the build and runtime dependencies for arbitrary version numbers, it is incomplete for reproducible builds since a precise bit-by-bit version is needed, and not every minor change or update might increase the noted version number [7, 19].

With a reproducible build, anyone can produce bit-by-bit identical build artifacts from the source code and all its dependencies. This is commonly verified by comparing the cryptographic hashes of multiple independent instances of build artifacts.

Different hardware structures can create new issues. In the context of this work, a consistent hardware structure of x86 will be assumed when comparing build artifacts. The CPU microcode can potentially introduce non-determinism into the build, but it is assumed not to do so.

3.2.1 Hermetic build systems

A fully documented build environment is necessary to implement reproducible builds. The appropriate tooling makes the build process independent of its host machine’s environment, as it only uses the explicitly documented build environment.

If every aspect that could influence the build is either set to a consistent default or explicitly defined. Executing the build while ignoring the host machine’s initial setup would be possible. This could be done by, for example, setting the build environment date and time to a default of 01:00 1.1.1970 and explicitly declaring every software dependency, including its exact version. Systems that enable this independence from their host machine’s standard environment are called hermetic build systems [42].

3.2.2 Effects of reproducible builds on supply chain security

The supply chain describes the dependency of software on other software. It is differentiated between **build-time dependencies** needed to compile the source code and **runtime dependencies** required to run the build artifacts afterward. In Figure 2, the direct and indirect runtime dependencies of glibc⁴ are shown. Since those dependencies are used as a functional basis for glibc, vulnerabilities, and malicious functionality can be inherited along with the rest. Those malicious functionalities can happen accidentally but also by explicitly targeting glibc, like in the case with liblzma in section 1.1 [35].

⁴<https://www.gnu.org/software/libc/>

Figure 2: A dependency graph for all glibc version 2.40-36 runtime dependencies.

With reproducible builds, the goal is to verify that a build artifact has been created from a specific source code. This verification is done by comparing cryptographic hashes created from multiple build results.

The concept of checksum verification, often used when, for example, downloading files from a third party, is applied to the build itself to make sure it has not been tampered with while running the build.

A third party often provides the resulting build artifacts (see Figure 1) through package managers, container image registries, or similar binary caches. Consequently, the two options are to either compile on a safe and local machine or trust that the third-party build process is free of malicious actions. Malicious actors can include a compromised machine as well as a trusted contributor.

Multiple independent build processes can build identical artifacts from the same source code if the build process is reproducible. Additional builds can now be used to verify the checksum that belongs to the initial public build artifact (see Figure 3). If the checksums are identical, it is proven that the public build artifacts are what they claim to be: the compiled source code without hidden modifications [25].

Since modern software almost always depends on other software, it uses many other build artifacts. All those artifacts construct multiple branches of the software supply chain, resulting in a dependency tree for yet another artifact. Some of those dependencies might not implement reproducible builds. If every dependency were a reproducible software build, it would be called bootstrappable. This special case will be discussed in the following chapter section 3.2.3.

Some dependencies are provided as precompiled artifacts not made with reproducible builds. Since these must be deemed trusted, there is no realistic way to verify the binary by oneself. In this case, there is no choice but to trust that the developer providing the dependency or a dependencies dependency produces a non-malicious binary. The attempt to recreate a reproducible artifact on a compromised machine that creates a malicious binary cannot be used for verification because it

Figure 3: Multiple independent build processes using the same source code create build artifacts. A computed checksum can be used to verify that they are identical.

will create a different checksum.

The more non-reproducible dependencies directly or indirectly affect the build process, the more parties need to be trusted, emphasizing the significance of the question "Who do we trust?". With reproducible builds and thus possible verification of the content of build artifacts, the number of parties can be reduced, as can the risk that comes when trusting a great number of individuals [46].

So what effect do reproducible builds have and have not? Reproducible builds are in no way "solving" software security. They are one step of many to get closer to safe software. Reproducible builds as a security measure only work assuming that the source code and the build process are trustworthy and not inherently malicious. If that were the case, the term "maliciously reproducible" can be used to describe a reproducible build process, but every time, it will result in malicious build artifacts. This case is mentioned in "trusting trust" where the C compiler, used to compile itself, can recognize the source code and inject a malicious sequence [46]. Every newly built C compiler will also be malicious, even if the source code is not. The concept of reproducible builds is decoupled from the content since malware can also use reproducible builds.

In the case of vendoring, the added files are a potential risk in terms of security and non-determinism. These additional sources must be considered trusted in the

same manner as the project source code itself.

Consequently, reproducible builds are only a security gain after every input has been declared non-malicious and trusted. Inputs mainly include the source code, every build dependency, and all parts of the build toolchain. After this “declaration of trust” and the corresponding artifact hash are computed, modifications, especially obfuscated ones, can be detected by comparing the hashes of multiple build results.

From a security perspective, the developers who can modify the source code and build process are assumed to be trusted. This includes the developer who initially set up the build system. The number of trusted people can be considerable, depending on the project size. Every one of those people is a potential security risk due to their access rights and can be targeted by an attack.

Social engineering attacks on developers exploit weaknesses in human cognitive functions [32]. For example [20]:

- Baiting: The attacker lures the victim with attractive promises like money to reveal critical information.
- Pretexting: Impersonating a higher authority individual to pressure the victim into giving up information.
- Phishing: Sending fraudulent emails that can be personalized to the victim to obtain critical information.

Due to the nature of a reproducible software build, tampering with the build process can be detected more easily and traced back to the compromised developer account that made the changes. Besides the initial security advantages, it disincentivizes an attack on individual developers [39].

To compare, an independent version that cannot be tampered with by the same developer is needed. This independent build is easily done in open-source software but not as easy in closed-source software.

3.2.3 Bootstrappable builds

Applying the concept of reproducible builds to dependencies continuously reduces the set of required binaries to the minimal subset necessary for bootstrapping an empty environment. It is not possible to construct such an environment entirely from source code alone; at least one minimal external compiler binary must be assumed to be trusted.

The implication is that a minimal set of binaries must be trusted by necessity regardless of which entities are deemed trustworthy by choice or policy. The more binaries can be verified with reproducible builds, the less trust is needed.

Anyone will end up with at least one compiler compiling another like the case for the C compiler GCC⁵. A compiler compiling another creates a chicken-and-egg problem because a initial compiler is necessary to obtain a compiler. Since binaries are extremely hard to verify by human inspections, a simpler initial compiler is commonly used.

Using the GNU Guix package manager⁶ as an example [18]. GCC, Binutils⁷ and the GNU C Library⁸ are generally taken for granted but are too large binary files, to be manually inspected. They are instead replaced with a smaller assembler and linker [17].

Figure 4: Bootstrap process for GCC 4.7.4 based on a third-party MesCC compiler binary.

These tools used in Figure 4 are still 145MB but smaller than the usual build tools, including GCC. With those, the 'missing' GCC, Binutils, and C Library can be built from their source code. The size of trusted third-party compiled binaries is reduced from 250MB to 145MB.

Ideally, this reduction is made to a binary that is so small that it is easily auditable and inspectable. A small binary with a single static application case, like the compilation of a more complex compiler, rarely needs modifications and reinspections. It enables a nearly complete local build of Software. In this case, the build process of any third party except the bootstrapping tools does not need to be trusted if it can be verified through a reproducible build instead.

⁵<https://gcc.gnu.org/>

⁶<https://guix.gnu.org/>

⁷<https://www.gnu.org/software/binutils/>

⁸<https://www.gnu.org/software/libc/>

A more tangible example would be Bitcoin⁹. Since an attack on Bitcoin would be highly profitable, the incentive to enable a binary to be checked by external parties is high. Furthermore, every build artifact used as a dependency should also be checked by independent third parties. It is exceptionally well suited since it is open source and has a high-security requirement due to being a high-value target. The combination between reproducible builds (maximize verification) and having as few externally built binaries as possible (minimize trust) is plausible [9].

3.3 Nix

Nix is an ecosystem consisting of three major parts: the language, the package manager, and the operating system (see Table 2).

The language	Nix
The package manager	nixpkgs
The operating system	NixOS

Table 2: Parts of the Nix ecosystem.

The language and the package manager will be focused on in this work. They are used as a tool to define and use build environments in a declarative way. The operating system can be used for configurable and reproducible run-time environments. It is not specific to single projects and is used for run-time environments, service composition, and deployment.

Lastly, even though everything can be compiled from source code, that does not mean it has to be. Because of reproducible builds, the individual builders can agree on a hash that verifies the binary’s contents. How numerous local builds can be skipped with Nix will be described in section 3.3.5.

3.3.1 Core concepts

Nix takes a unique approach to filesystem utilization and software component/software package management [13].

In this work, a component is defined as a discrete software unit that either provides or depends on functionality via the file system. It represents a singular deployment entity suitable for automated composition. Integration with other components may occur through various mechanisms, including static linking, dynamic linking, source code inclusion, and other methods. A component’s provision or functionality consumption can be categorized into two temporal domains: build-time and run-time.

⁹<https://bitcoin.org/>

Figure 5: Two steps to realize a Nix expression into the corresponding Nix store component.

Nix introduces restrictions on the filesystem usage for storing software components. Besides access permissions, few to no rules are imposed on the file system by the Linux Filesystem Hierarchy Standard (LFHS). Where software is installed is considered a best practice model or standard, but there is no real enforcement [27]. For example, installing `hello` with `APT`¹⁰ will place files compliant with LFHS at `/usr/bin` and `/usr/share`. Nix is not compliant with the LFHS. Every software component is stored under a unique path in the Nix store and, if necessary, linked with a symbolic link to another path (see section 3.3.4).

The characteristic of the LFHS derives from the fact that memory (RAM) and storage (disk) are part of a storage hierarchy but are handled with very different rules depending on the programming language used because there are little to no constraints on the disk level. Nix takes concepts from programming and memory management, such as immutability and garbage collection, and applies them at the file system level [13].

Assuming a software component c is installed, it resides in its location with the path $p = path(c)$. This path can be used to dereference c as $c = dereference(p)$. A component path is functionally equal to a pointer used to reference a position in memory.

To implement the above, Nix uses two steps to realize declared components as shown in Figure 5.

The Nix expression is written using the Nix language. It describes the software

¹⁰<https://documentation.ubuntu.com/server/how-to/software/package-management/index.html>

component requirements to be built and run as intended. A Nix derivation is a step between the expression and the result. A static text file declaring all inputs and the build instructions required to realize (i.e., compile, download, or otherwise obtain the artifacts) the software component. The Nix expression can include a package without a specific version. Versioning outside of the Expression is possible through a lock file or the host machine state. A derivation combines the Nix expression with the explicit version to create a definitive package description. Once it is saved in the Nix store, it is called a store derivation.

A Nix store object is a store derivation that has been realized. It consists of filesystem objects and store paths to reference other required store objects. The set of store paths is called a closure and includes the previously declared dependencies. It is marked as valid in the Nix database after every referenced store object is marked as valid.

3.3.2 Nix language

The Nix language is designed and used to create and compose precise descriptions how existing files (e.g., source code files, compiler binaries) are used to derive new files (i.e., build artifacts).

Domain-specific: There are functions built into the language to integrate with the Nix store, which manages files and performs the derivations declared in the Nix language (see section 3.3.4).

Declarative: There is no notion of executing sequential steps. Dependencies between operations are established only through data.

Pure: Values cannot change during computation. A function always produces the same output if its input does not change. However, certain built-in functions exhibit behavior dependent on the host machine's characteristics, leading to non-deterministic or platform-specific outputs.

Functional: Functions are handled like any other value. They can be assigned to names, taken as arguments, or returned by functions like a primitive data type.

Lazy: Values are only computed when they are needed. It enables the definition of large sets of Nix expressions without actually computing values to improve the performance for complex package sets.

Dynamically typed: Type errors are only detected when expressions are evaluated. [2]

The following presents a concise overview of the syntactic structure of the Nix language. In addition to basic data types, there are lists (e.g., [1 2 3]), attribute sets (e.g., { x = 1; y = 2; }), and functions (e.g., x: x + 1). Some general syntax rules include [2]:

- The **let-in** statement is used to assign names to values. Values can be primitive data types, lists, attribute sets, and functions.

- Setting name and value of a **variable** is used by writing the variable's name on the left side of = and the value on the right. The statement is closed with a semicolon.
- When using **functions**, the arguments are given by writing them with a space in between.

The language describes software dependencies to run and deploy everything that is needed. The Nix expression in Listing 1 does the following [13]:

1. Variables are declared to be used in the following line.
2. The Nix Packages collection (nixpkgs) is assigned to the pkgs name by importing the host machines state.
3. A function to make all Letters of a String into Uppercase is assigned the myUpperCase name.
4. The function myUpperCase is called with a String as an argument.

```

1 let
2   pkgs = import <nixpkgs> {};
3   myUpperCase = pkgs.lib.strings.toUpper
4 in
5   myUppercase "lookup paths considered harmful"
6
7 # Output: "LOOKUP PATHS CONSIDERED HARMFUL"

```

Listing 1: Example of Nix language usage [1]

3.3.3 Derivations

The most essential function of the Nix language is **derivation** or **mkDerivation**. They are used to create a single specific and static software component. Derivations are the second of three layers of the Nix deployment model (see Figure 5). Every derivation will be saved with a unique path in the Nix store derived from its content using cryptographic hashing (see section 3.3.4). They exist so changes to the Nix language can be made without invalidating store paths (created with cryptographic hashing) of the already built static input addressed store derivations [13].

Because it includes every file used as an input, it can be used to produce the output files repeatedly [29]. This makes the build process reliably repeatable, which is not the same as a reproducible build since the build results may slightly differ each time.

Figure 6: Dependency tree of package D before and after dependency A has been updated.

There are three types of derivations, with the last being marked as an experimental feature due to an incomplete implementation.

Input addressed derivations are the kind described above. They store every derivation used as an input to create the output artifacts. To build these, every derivation used as a dependency has to be built or exist in the Nix store. This dependency on other derivations cascades down to lower-level packages like the static compiler used to compile GCC. When everything except the output path where the build artifacts will be placed is collected, a hash over the file content s is used to generate the missing path:

$$outPath = nixStoreDir + "/" + printHash32(truncate(20, hashsha256(s))) + " - " + name [13].$$

A problem with input-addressed derivations are mass rebuilds. A dependency change in input-addressed derivations will trigger rebuilds on everything downstream regardless of the change (see Figure 6). The input still changes if a change does not affect the build output. Even if these changes would not alter any downstream binaries, the store derivations used as a dependency changed. In a worst-case scenario, a very low-level dependency (e.g., glibc) does trigger a massive number of builds.

Fixed output derivations are used for external resources. Besides build outputs and derivation files, the actual source code is also an input that needs to be packaged for the Nix store. These derivations are utilized to retrieve known content, such as the contents of a Git repository at a specified commit. Since a

URL is not guaranteed to provide the content expected, it might lead to impurities. The provided contents hash and the expected hash are compared to counteract impurities [13].

Floating content addressed derivations aim for a more dynamic local management of Nix store components (e.g., installed packages). They try to solve the impracticality of input-addressed derivations regarding mass rebuilds. They aim to solve the problem of mass rebuilds occurring when using input-addressed derivation. Assume the software components in Figure 6 are content addressed. A change of A into A' creates a new derivation, but this change does not affect the build output of B (i.e., $A! = A'$ and $B = B'$). Then, the build of a C' is unnecessary because no direct inputs from the previous definition of C changed due to the differences in A . This modification would change C' in the updated field of Figure 6 to the C used in the version 1 field [13].

3.3.4 Nix store

The Nix store is the directory where every store derivation and downloaded or built component is stored. It is usually found at `/nix/store/`. This directory is immutable, and changes should only happen through Nix. The content of those components varies, but all are world readable.

Every Nix store component is named in the scheme `/nix/store/<hash>-<name>-<version>`. This is the case for directories and single files that include the additional file format extension. A store derivation (a derivation file inside the Nix store) path for bash could look like `/nix/store/s63zivn27i8qv5cqiy8r5hf48r323qwa-bash-5.2p37.drv`.

Once a store component is created, it shall be immutable and, in filesystem terms, read-only. It can only be removed when any other component does not depend on it. For example, uninstalling a software component would not remove it from the machine. Uninstalling merely removes the executable from the current PATH. When the garbage collection is executed, the component and any other unneeded store path will be deleted from the Nix store and, consequently, the machine [13].

A store derivation, besides other things, includes the direct dependencies of this software component. The respective store derivations of those dependencies are created recursively. In the Nix expression and subsequent derivation of the component, dependencies are divided between build and run-time.

Those dependencies can be queried recursively, and this sum of dependencies is called a closure. The closure is a list of software components required to deploy the current component. It is also tracked outside the store derivation files and used for successful deployment and garbage collection. Inspecting the closure of an already built software component, the “outPath” written in a derivation, reveals a much shorter list of only run-time dependencies.

In Figure 7 example, paths from a Nix store and arrows indicating dependency on another store component can be seen. Obtaining the whole dependency graph, including version numbers, is straightforward using Nix cli tools.

Figure 7: Filesystem tree example of Nix components that link dependencies.

To realize a store derivation means running the component’s build as described or downloading it pre-built from a substitutor (see section 3.3.5). This includes at least all run-time dependencies, possibly making this a recursive operation.

When building the component, source code is fetched, build instructions are executed in a temporary directory, and the resulting artifacts are copied to their declared output path inside the Nix store. Once all dependencies and the derivations output are inside the Nix store, a store path will be marked as valid. The garbage collection will not delete a valid path.

The structuring of the Nix store allows for multiple installed versions of software if needed. Compared to container images, it still allows a dependency to be used by various other packages if they depend on the identical package [13].

3.3.5 Substitution of builds with a binary cache

Substituting builds can significantly shorten the realization of derivations. Its practical use includes a dedicated builder and a, in comparison, often weaker machine to run the built artifacts.

When an input derivation is created, the output path of that build result is known. The output path is a unique identifier for the inputs that can be used as a pointer. Before a derivation is realized by building the artifacts, the output path is looked up on a list of trusted substitutors (sometimes called binary caches). A substitutor hosts “outPaths” with their build artifacts so other machines can download them and skip a local build. A download will replace the local build if the output path is cached in the substitutor.

If a substitutor is available to realize a store path, build-time dependencies can be disregarded, as no actual build process occurs. Consequently, these dependencies are not required in the local Nix store.

4 Non-deterministic builds in nixpkgs

Nixpkgs, as the public package management infrastructure, can be considered State-of-the-Art. A specialized CI software “Hydra” is used to build Nix expressions. Hydra is a wrapper around CLI commands like `nix-build` to interact with Nix. In a few cases, such as the NixOS minimal installer ISO, a report can be generated with an existing tool [37]. However, there are no automatically and periodically performed tests if builds are deterministic. A single package update with re-evaluation of the Nix expression, build, and upload to the public substitutor can take 3 to 5 days. Due to the number of packages and hardware resources, building every package twice is impossible, especially because the advantages of reproducible builds for numerous packages would not outweigh the cost of implementation.

Testing is only done by individual users by comparing a local build result from the source code with the build results in the public substitutor (see section 3.3.5). For example, to build `Nix build nixpkgs#hello` would substitute the build with a download from the cache at `cache.nixos.org`. Building locally with `Nix build nixpkgs#hello --rebuild` compares the build artifacts with the ones in the Nix Store that were obtained from the substitutor. This singular rebuild only tests the derivation that defines the hello package and none of the dependencies. A report for a non-deterministic build is reported and tracked with GitHub issues¹¹. Two examples for non-reproducible packages can be seen in Table 3.

Package Name	Reasons for Non-Determinism
<code>java-service-wrapper</code> ¹²	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• timestamps in jar artifacts
<code>github-runner</code> ¹³	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• timestamps• non-human readable sections

Table 3: Some known non-deterministic packages in nixpkgs.

¹¹<https://github.com/NixOS/nixpkgs/issues>

5 Approach

Testing is the best option for finding non-determinism in a build process, but it does not guarantee a deterministic build. In the following chapters, it will be assumed that the impurities not found by testing do not exist until proven otherwise. Two examples of impurities that might not be found with a second build are:

1. hardware architecture: non-determinism due to microcode, scheduling, differences between Intel, AMD, and their different CPU generations
2. presently hidden long-term impurities: as with a complete timestamp, it is possible only to have the year, decade, or century included. Testing within an ecological hardware and energy usage (only once or twice and immediately on source changes) might not necessarily find it. Testing a package in January 2024 with the current decade included will not cause a test to find the non-determinism for a long time. However, the non-determinism due to the included current decade is found in any other decade.

The chosen approach is to rebuild every dependency in the build closure. It verifies whether or not a package built is bootstrappable (see section 3.2.3). If not, the store derivation path found to be non-reproducible is reported to a developer to evaluate and take action. In case no non-determinism is found, it is safe to assume every dependency is reproducibly buildable. In this case, the trusting trust issue first described by Thompson et al. only affects the bootstrapping binaries and none of the remaining dependencies [46].

A local build is necessary for this step because the built artifacts Nix creates have no metadata about their origin. A substitutor could potentially provide build artifacts of another substitutor instead of separately built ones. The Client downloading both by substitutor-provided files might assume they were built individually and can be compared to mark this build as reproducible when the artifacts originate from the same built process [42].

The presented test method consumes significant computing resources because of numerous compilation jobs. Nonetheless, it is an additional measure that does not interfere with an existent CI infrastructure seen in Figure 8 and does not worsen the execution time of existing builds and tests measurably.

The implementation diagram Figure 9 shows the flow of information in the approach. An existing Gitlab instance triggers an existing CI runner to start the pipeline (see section 3.1.2). A package build is defined in the pipeline instructions. Optionally the upload to a private substitutor is done (see section 3.3.5). Additionally, inside the pipeline, a script `getclosure <server_url>` is run immediately after the build to collect the full build closure and the merge request identification information to send both to the tracking server (see section 5.1).

Figure 8: Existing CI infrastructure.

Figure 9: Information flow in an implementation that combines the above-described technology to track and create reproducibility reports for the whole build closure.

The tracking server imports received store derivations from the build closure and starts the rebuilding (see section 5.2) of only untested store derivations (see section 5.3).

Upon every build closure received with information about a merge request, the tracking server sends an HTTP request to create a merge comment over the GitLab¹⁴ API that displays the bootstrappability status of a Nix package. If non-reproducible packages are found, their store derivations will be listed.

In the following subsections, every essential component for the implementation is approached as an individual topic.

5.1 Requesting a test in the CI pipeline

Because of the restriction not to interfere with current CI runtimes to a moderate degree, the second build of every build closure element cannot be made within the CI pipeline. Consequently, another machine is needed to build packages for the reproducibility tests.

Since a Nix expression does not have to be version pinned and can rely on a host machine's state of nixpkgs, the Nix expression is not a reliable primary key to store data about its deterministic build behavior. Instead, the store derivation (see section 3.3.3) with static content and a uniquely identifiable file path are used.

When a reproducibility test is needed, an executable on the CI runner host is executed right after the build. A HTTP request will be sent to the tracking server with the following parts of information:

- **The top-level package** will indicate what Nix expression has a non-deterministic build closure element in case one is found and reported.
- **Merge request metadata** includes the merge request identifier and the repositories identifier to be used in section 5.4 to direct the test result message.
- **A list of store derivation paths** are the build closure. Every one of those paths needs to be rebuilt to test for a non-deterministic package.
- **A partially exported Nix store** including every immutable derivation file included in the build closure as a byte stream. Ensuring the availability of these files over a private substitutor was considered but abandoned due to constraints on available infrastructure.

The tracking server will import the previously partially exported Nix store to ensure they are available for building the artifacts in the derivations `outPath`. Every machine used exclusively as a builder is not a reliable source for store derivations

¹⁴<https://about.gitlab.com/>

because they typically run a regular and automated garbage collection on their Nix store.

5.2 Rebuilding store derivations

One report includes the build closure in the form of a list of store paths. Other elements besides store derivation paths are also included in the build closure. For example, shell scripts or patch files. Without an associated derivation, it is not known how to create or recreate these store components. Before rebuilding, every path that is not a store derivation is removed from the list of rebuilt elements. When rebuilding for every element of the remaining list, the following is done:

1. The command `nix-build /nix/store/<hash>-<name>-<version>.drv` will initially realize the derivations `outPath` if it is not yet in the local store. Every available substitutor will be used to look up the `outPath` and download the artifacts if possible. A local build is performed if the artifacts, including their run-time closure, are not available in the public or a private substitutor. The local Nix store now holds the build instructions (store derivation) and the output artifacts of those instructions (`outPath` content).
2. The command `nix-build /nix/store/<hash>-<name>-<version>.drv --check` will start a local build of the package. When it is done, a comparison between the existent artifacts inside the store and the newly created ones is made. If these artifacts are identical, the build is considered reproducible. If the artifacts differ the build is impure and at some stage non-determinism is introduced.

When a non-deterministic store derivation is found, Nix default behavior only announces a difference existing between the artifacts. Using a `diff-hook` to execute `diffoscope`¹⁵ upon finding non-determinism, the relevant sections are printed to `stdout`. Some formats are known by the `diffoscope` tool and are printed in a human-readable way instead of hexadecimal encoding (e.g., timestamp formats or similar ASCII¹⁶ encoded sections).

A compilation process can use a large amount of computing resources. The response time of the tracking server may be negatively impacted when performing builds in parallel. Nix provides the ability to build remotely. By doing this, the actual load-heavy building phase can be outsourced to another machine connectable over an SSH connection using a trusted user. The distributed builds functionality allows remote builds to be automatically done on the best-suited machine. This

¹⁵<https://diffoscope.org/>

¹⁶<https://www.ascii-code.com>

includes compilation for different hardware structures. Upon testing, the rebuild functionality is not fully implemented with the distributed builds. For now, a static remote builder is used instead of a list of builders. One tracking server can only compile one hardware structure depending on the build machine chosen (unless virtualization is used on the builder). Utilizing remote builder functionality allows for the tracking server to run, in comparison, weaker hardware and be able to capitalize on existing build infrastructure. Increasing or decreasing hardware performance for the builder is also made trivial.

5.3 Tracking tested store derivations

A whole build closure includes many dependencies in the standard environment for every Nix build. Additionally, similar projects might use identical dependencies. Testing such a massive number of packages repeatedly for every requested test wastes hardware resources. Nonetheless, for every new version of the standard environment, many packages must be tested again.

A simple SQLite¹⁷ database will suffice to record test results. The required information is the store derivation path as the primary key and the build reproducibility status as value. The store derivation path is a unique identifier for a nix store object (see section 3.3.4). The entry is created upon the first build and modified as soon as the second build is done. Differentiating between reasons for non-determinism or even a failed build can be made but is not mandatory. For example, a failing initial build that can not be substituted could fail. In this case, strictly speaking, the build is not reproducible and not even repeatable. This can happen if resources such as source code are unavailable. An error due to local misconfiguration is possible and, most importantly, fixable. An error from a third party (e.g., source code provider) changing can hardly be corrected.

In subsequent future use cases, a second table records the derivations outPath and the associated content hash. As seen in Figure 3, these content hashes can be used like a checksum to compare artifacts produced by independent build machines to verify their integrity. However, it is possible for a compromised toolchain to only affect a specifically targeted build process, making it harder to apply this checksum comparison concept in practice [46, 42].

5.4 Reporting test results

To provide a practical value from these asynchronous tests, the results need to be brought to the developer's attention in a non-invasive yet convenient way [21]. The goal is to inform a developer about non-determinism in work related to him so it

¹⁷<https://sqlite.org/index.html>

can be fixed, reported upstream, or ignored. Adopting reproducible builds is not always desirable or a priority [8].

To enable a good adoption of this new tooling, the test results need to be conveniently presented [4]. Focusing on what the developer needs from this test is essential so that only the necessary information is passed on [45, 21].

The restrictions are using a self-hosted GitLab instance and the execution time not being within the CI pipeline. Testing the whole build closure will result in an unknown execution time, and due to tracking tested store derivations, it will also differ in time when repeated.

When a whole build closure is done by either rebuilding or reusing past test results, a test result message is constructed. There are two possible outcomes:

- **No non-determinism found:** Every element of the build closure has been rebuilt, and there have been no findings of non-determinism. The feedback message only needs to include what package has been tested, how many elements are in the build closure, how many are testable derivations, and that none of those were found to build non-deterministic or not at all.
- **At least one case of non-determinism found:** At least one store derivation cannot be built reproducibly. In addition to the information provided, when nothing is found, a list of paths of non-deterministic store derivations is added. Because the number of non-deterministic store derivations is of an unknown quantity, including the diffoscope outputs is impractical [45]. Instead, instructions to reproduce the test of individual store derivations have been added.

Using the GitLab instance to report the test results, the first option, GitLab issues, is not fit for the following reasons:

- High number of duplicated issues: If a low-level dependency used in many other projects is non-reproducible, an identical issue would appear in all repositories. There is a realistic chance to drown out critical issues or antagonize developers, who see potentially many issues as a nuisance [4].
- Stale issues: With a large build closure, there is a potential to create many issues at once. This might make developers consider the tooling bordering spam.
- Issue automation: Issues are primarily created manually only after a developer considers the issue fixable in this repository and important enough to be tracked.

Instead, the assumption is only to request test results within a Gitlab merge request. Commenting on merge requests is more practical because:

- **Ignoring a dependency** is easily possible. A package building non-reproducibly because of upstream issues might be out of the developer's control. Reporting this at the correct upstream repository might be the only possible action available.
- **Reporting “no non-determinism found”** is an informative message similar to usual build logs, ensuring the test ran but not creating lasting messages beyond the current merge request.
- **Tied to specific commit** the point in time when the test is finished is less relevant than commit association.

6 Test results

This section will take two Nix expressions: “stable” in Listing 2 has a deterministic build, and “unstable” in Listing 4 has a non-deterministic build. These examples show a result resembling expectations of the test results. Other packages are tested afterward.

The first Nix expression in Listing 2 creates a Nix store component that consists of a singular text file with four numbers in it. When tested within a merge request, a comment announces that no non-determinism was found Listing 3.

```
1 let
2   nixpkgs = fetchTarball "https://github.com/NixOS/nixpkgs/
   archive/9747612b3ddff37b43767fbda6f9e0db820c4f57.tar.
   gz";
3   pkgs = import nixpkgs {};
4 in {
5   stable = pkgs.runCommand "stable" {} ''
6     echo 5432 > $out
7   '';
8 }
```

Listing 2: A deterministic Nix build producing a static text file.

```
1 Report ready for /nix/store/
   crnnzxdy1n69ns9rsg2n0qbpkjkq8yxz-stable.drv.
2 From all 323 closure elements there are 225 derivations.
3 (225/0/0) reproducible/non-reproducible/error
```

Listing 3: A Gitlab comment created by testing Listing 2.

The second Nix expression in Listing 4 results in a Gitlab merge comment notifying about detected non-determinism Listing 5.

```
1 let
2   nixpkgs = fetchTarball "https://github.com/NixOS/nixpkgs/
   archive/9747612b3ddff37b43767fbda6f9e0db820c4f57.tar.
   gz";
3   pkgs = import nixpkgs {};
4 in {
5   stable = pkgs.runCommand "stable" {} ''
6     echo $RANDOM > $out
7     '';
8 }
```

Listing 4: A non-deterministic Nix build producing a text file with a random number.

```
1 Report ready for /nix/store/4
   z3fl9mcv1ldxzs1g7z84p4v6x5mgb9p-unstable.drv.
2 From all 323 closure elements there are 225 derivations.
3 (224/1/0) reproducible/non-reproducible/error
4 Non-Reproducible:
5 - /nix/store/4z3fl9mcv1ldxzs1g7z84p4v6x5mgb9p-unstable.drv
6
7 to build a non-reproducible derivation yourself to inspect
   the differences do the following:
8 - checkout this commit
9 - build the package: nix build .#default (actual build
   command might vary see pipeline script; will substitute
   if possible)
10 - rebuild to get all logs for one derivation: nix-build /
   nix/store/4z3fl9mcv1ldxzs1g7z84p4v6x5mgb9p-unstable.drv
   --check (depending on the package and remote builder
   usage this can take seconds to a few minutes or longer)
11 - compare both versions with the diffoscope tool nix run
   nixpkgs#diffoscope -- <outPath> <outPath>.check
```

Listing 5: A Gitlab comment created by testing Listing 4.

Comparing both outputs, as shown in Listing 6 and knowing the expression, it is clear that the random number is causing the difference between the two build results.

```
1 $ diffoscope /nix/store/6nfp9cn010v23ag6820gcyg56f3165cv-
  unstable /nix/store/6nfp9cn010v23ag6820gcyg56f3165cv-
  unstable.check
2 --- /nix/store/6nfp9cn010v23ag6820gcyg56f3165cv-unstable
3 +++ /nix/store/6nfp9cn010v23ag6820gcyg56f3165cv-unstable.
  check
4 @@ -1 +1 @@
5 -24737
6 +12779
```

Listing 6: A comparison between two outputs of Listing 4.

These two expressions provide a minimal example as a use case.

Applying the test on the tracking service repository itself reveals the test result message seen in Figure 10.

The screenshot shows a GitLab merge comment titled "post_merge_comments" from a bot. The comment reports on a reproducibility test for a specific derivation. It states that out of 1236 closure elements, there are 1019 derivations that are reproducible, 1018/1/0 are non-reproducible, and there is 1 non-reproducible error. A list of derivations is provided, with one highlighted as non-reproducible. Below the list, instructions are given on how to inspect the differences, including checking out a commit, building the package, rebuilding to get logs, and comparing versions with the diffoscope tool.

Figure 10: A GitLab merge comment created by testing the tracking service itself.

In this case, only one of the 1020 derivations is not reproducible. Following the instructions below the listed derivation, the recreation of full build logs results in the error message seen in Listing 7.

```
error: hash mismatch in fixed-output derivation '/nix/store
/jb217201xnaq8wfx0i4hmyqjg35cfxvj-1
e8df9e85a1ff213e5868bd822877695f27504ad.patch.drv':
specified: sha256-EX+PYGicK73lsL/J0kSZ4S5y1/
NHic1BddhsnV6NPPI=
```

```

got:      sha256-
         ohjgqbgwNSazhVHaiD3bwIoIJRA635Q3tko3Gxmp27M=
error: build of '/nix/store/
         zzl2mdjnlc7b33xj9gh77xk5wa0zm1ns-1
         e8df9e85a1ff213e5868bd822877695f27504ad.patch.drv '
         failed

```

Listing 7: Output from a failed build of a fixed output derivation.

As described in section 3.3.3, a fixed output derivation should pull an expected resource from a URL and compare it with the previously set resource hash to ensure it did not change. In this case, the resource provided changed, making the fixed output derivation unbuildable and, consequently, non-reproducible.

In another case testing the `github-runner` package in `nixpkgs` mentioned in section 4 yields a comment as seen in Figure 11.

Figure 11: A GitLab merge comment created by testing the `github-runner` version corresponding to the build machines `nixpkgs` version.

It is not only a dependency but the top-level package that introduces non-determinism in two files. Following the diffoscope instructions, comparing both `github-runner` store paths as seen in Listing 8 a simple time stamp is revealed to be at least one cause for the non-deterministic build.

```

COFF Header:
                Machine: 0x8664
                Sections: 0x0002
-                Time stamp: 0x8bebf674
+                Time stamp: 0xf5f917f4

```

```

    Pointer to Symbol Table: 0x00000000
          Symbol Count: 0x00000000
    Optional Header Size: 0x00f0
          Characteristics: 0x2022

```

Listing 8: Output snippet of the upmost file after using the diffoscope tool to inspect build artifacts.

The second, however, is not recognized by the diffoscope tool. It is displayed as hexadecimal encoded sections blocks in Listing 9.

```

00000050: 2c4c 0000 0400 0000 2355 5300 304c 0000  ,L
    .....#US.0L..
00000060: 8000 0000 2347 5549 4400 0000 b04c 0000  ....#
    GUID....L..
-00000070: a087 0000 2342 6c6f 6200 0000 0f35 04cf  ....#
    Blob....5..
-00000080: b289 944f b96c 9093 770d 23af 29f9 7f83  ...0.l
    ..w.#.)...
+00000070: a087 0000 2342 6c6f 6200 0000 a9f5 78fd  ....#
    Blob.....x.
+00000080: a300 1340 b415 4d37 4598 c4ba 812e 09f2  ...@..
    M7E.....
00000090: 0000 0000 579f b62b 091e 0000 0100 0000  ....W
    ..+.....
000000a0: 4201 0000 c900 0000 d303 0000 2f03 0000  B
    ...../...

```

Listing 9: Output snippet of the second listed file after using the diffoscope tool to inspect build artifacts.

Those samples provide three possible sources for non-determinism in a build:

- an external resource such as source code is not available anymore
- the date and time are included in the build artifacts
- non-human readable sections differ between builds

The developer can take action to inform upstream about the non-reproducible dependency resource being unavailable.

Since the second part, Listing 9, showed only issues in the top-level package, the developer can take action himself if he desires to. He can set the build environment date and time to a consistent value to remove the easier of the two issues. The second will need a not-yet-obvious or known solution to fix.

7 Summary

The implementation of reproducible and bootstrappable builds is not nearly as widespread as their awareness and perception of them as a seal of quality.

When implemented, reproducible builds can help discover compromised build machines and toolchains due to deviations in the build artifacts. Comparing hashes from artifacts produced by separate build machines enables a simple yet effective method to discover malicious software artifacts. Historically, attacks against build toolchains have been executed successfully with no guarantee of stopping. A differentiation between closed and open source is unnecessary, especially if it is security-critical software either way.

Rebuilding every package and every package in the build closure as described in section 5 gives an overview of the number of non-deterministic builds of included software.

The implementation results in section 6 show that a Nix package can be automatically tested for non-deterministic builds in its build closure to declare software as bootstrappable. Every build closure element without a reproducible build can pose a hard-to-detect vulnerability. The number of non-reproducible builds can be used as a measurable indicator of the degree to which a piece of software is bootstrappable. The implementation approach integrates into an existing CI environment without influencing established build runtimes. Within the constraints of this work, a GitLab merge request comment is used to report test results. In general, a form that is perceived as optional should be used. More often than not, reproducible builds are not a very high priority. Awareness of the current state enables but does not necessarily force a prompt implementation of a reproducible build. It is the first step, regardless. A decision on what action should be taken depending on the test result is left to the developer.

8 Outlook

Improving the given implementation: While the GitLab merge comments work, there is potential for a better, graph-like, visualization. Visualization features like finding packages with inherited non-determinism due to a non-reproducible dependency or other graph database-like features to query the dependency tree could be beneficial.

In the current state, the rebuilding of derivations is implemented to happen one at a time. This results in plenty of CPU idle due to I/O wait times. A parallel approach dependent on hardware limitations, similar to Nix's behavior when building expressions, would benefit overall performance.

The implemented service's use of telemetry and monitoring is a technical shortcoming for practical application. More extensive monitoring possibilities enable more efficient use of hardware and more certainty about the health of the tracking service.

Collaborating with and integrating other efforts: In a prototype from Julien Malka, a hash collecting service is proposed to collect signed build output hashes from trusted builders [24]. Integrating the functionality to supply his prototype with build output hashes and using this service hash collection to verify a reproducible package to skip local builds could provide economic advantages.

Adding builder metadata, as Schwaighofer et al. suggested, makes it possible to differentiate build results by actual build origin [42]. The local rebuild could then be skipped if multiple builders produced traceable identical results independently.

The unstable Nix feature content addressed derivations: Content addressable derivations are currently considered highly experimental. The output path for build artifacts is calculated with a hash of the content itself, as described in section 3.3.3. Input addressed derivations calculate the output path only over all the input information.

The ability for an early build cut-off is described in section 3.3.3. This characteristic can prevent mass rebuilds because it can recognize if an input change (e.g., source code changes or updates) would affect the downstream build artifacts. Since the method to test for non-determinism is a second build, this early cut-off would prevent numerous builds where the output artifacts did not change compared to a differently named and tested version.

At this point, the rebuild functionality that is used in section 5.2 is not functional for content addressable derivations ¹⁸.

¹⁸<https://github.com/NixOS/nix/issues/11315>

Other Nix features are still in development. Especially distributed builds and remote building are complex implementations. The nix-daemon would pick the best builder with a fitting hardware structure so native compilation when rebuilding can be made easier, more attainable, and more efficient like it already does for a initial build.

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A Appendix

Installing hello with APT and Nix

```
1 $ podman run -it ubuntu:20.04 /bin/bash -c "apt update &&
  apt install -y hello && dpkg-query -L hello"
2 /.
3 /usr
4 /usr/bin
5 /usr/bin/hello
6 /usr/share
7 /usr/share/doc
8 /usr/share/doc/hello
9 /usr/share/doc/hello/NEWS.gz
10 /usr/share/doc/hello/changelog.Debian.gz
11 /usr/share/doc/hello/copyright
12 /usr/share/info
13 /usr/share/info/hello.info.gz
14 /usr/share/man
15 /usr/share/man/man1
16 /usr/share/man/man1/hello.1.gz
```

Listing 10: Installing hello in a ubuntu podman container with apt and listing the file locations (output shortened).

```
1 $ podman run -it ghcr.io/nixos/nix sh -c "nix --extra-
  experimental-features nix-command --extra-experimental-
  features flakes build nixpkgs#hello && nix-store -q
  result | cat && nix --extra-experimental-features nix-
  command --extra-experimental-features flakes build
  nixpkgs#hello && nix-store -q result | xargs ls"
2 /nix/store/y4qpcibkj767szhjb58i2sidmz8m24hb-hello-2.12.1
3 bin share
```

Listing 11: Installing hello package in a nixos podman container from nixpkgs with Nix and listing the file locations.

Nix derivation example

```
1 Derive(  
2 [  
3   ("out", "/nix/store/arv945sv85qcs4q3wlv5y6ify5jy8ia-  
4     stable", "", "")  
5 ],  
6 [  
7   ("/nix/store/s63zivn27i8qv5cqiy8r5hf48r323qwa-bash-5.2p37  
8     .drv", ["out"]),  
9   ("/nix/store/ws0w1jw9y3wmmvm305m18ivjil4nayls-stdenv-  
10     linux.drv", ["out"])  
11 ],  
12 ["/nix/store/v6x3cs394jgqfbi0a42pam708flxaphh-default-  
13     builder.sh"  
14 ],  
15 "x86_64-linux",  
16 ["/nix/store/p6k7xp1lsfmbdd731mlglrdj2d66mr82-bash-5.2p37/  
17     bin/bash",  
18 [ "-e", "/nix/store/v6x3cs394jgqfbi0a42pam708flxaphh-default  
19     -builder.sh"  
20 ],  
21 [ ("  
22   ("__structuredAttrs", ""),  
23   ("buildCommand", "echo 5432 > $out\n"),  
24   ("buildInputs", ""),  
25   ("builder", "/nix/store/p6k7xp1lsfmbdd731mlglrdj2d66mr82-  
26     bash-5.2p37/bin/bash"),  
27   ("cmakeFlags", ""),  
28   ("configureFlags", ""),  
29   ("depsBuildBuild", ""),  
30   ("depsBuildBuildPropagated", ""),  
31   ("depsBuildTarget", ""),  
32   ("depsBuildTargetPropagated", ""),  
33   ("depsHostHost", ""),  
34   ("depsHostHostPropagated", ""),  
35   ("depsTargetTarget", ""),  
36   ("depsTargetTargetPropagated", ""),  
37   ("doCheck", "")
```

```

33 ("doInstallCheck", ""),
34 ("enableParallelBuilding", "1"),
35 ("enableParallelChecking", "1"),
36 ("enableParallelInstalling", "1"),
37 ("mesonFlags", ""),
38 ("name", "stable"),
39 ("nativeBuildInputs", ""),
40 ("out", "/nix/store/arv945sv85qcs4q3w1w5y6ify5jy8ia-
    stable"),
41 ("outputs", "out"),
42 ("passAsFile", "buildCommand"),
43 ("patches", ""),
44 ("propagatedBuildInputs", ""),
45 ("propagatedNativeBuildInputs", ""),
46 ("stdenv", "/nix/store/spb2bpcnw0gbbr4x94cq8xs9n72hipwj-
    stdenv-linux"),
47 ("strictDeps", ""),
48 ("system", "x86_64-linux")
49 ]
50 )

```

Listing 12: Full derivation `/nix/store/crnzxdy1n69ns9rsg2n0qbpkjkq8yxz-stable.drv` created from Listing 2 and manually edited for readability

Declaration of Authorship

I confirm that this Master's thesis is my own work and I have documented all sources, tools and material used.

Date, place

Conrad Bandt